

ISSN (P) : 2321-290X ★ (E) 2349-980X

VOL:-X,ISSUE:-IX May 2023

RNI No. : UPBIL/2013/55327

Srinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

Peer Reviewed / Refereed Journal

Publisher : Social Research Foundation, Kanpur
(SRF International)

— Impact Factor —

SJIF = 7.723 (2023)

SJIF = 6.746 (2020)

GIF = 0.543 (2015)

IJIF = 6.038 (2018)

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8395365

(This DOI is not applicable for separate papers)

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सम्पादकीय.....

सुधी पाठकों,

मित्रों, भारतीय शिक्षा की त्रासदी यह है कि सत्तासीन व सत्ता से बाहर सभी राजनेता व शिक्षाविद् इसके महत्व और मानव-निर्माण के महत्व को स्वीकार तो करते हैं किन्तु इस तरफ कोई ध्यान नहीं देते- यहाँ तक कि इसकी उपेक्षा भी करते रहे हैं। आर्थिक विकास की तुलना में हम विकास की तुलना में हम विकास के इस सर्वोत्तम साधन को बहुत गौण स्थान देते रहे हैं। निःसन्देह प्राथमिक शिक्षा को राष्ट्र के विकास की नींव माना जाता है लेकिन वही क्षेत्र सबसे ज्यादा उपेक्षित रहा है। अपने ही प्रदेश में प्राथमिक विद्यालयों की हालत किसी से छुपी नहीं है। अधिकांश शिक्षकों के पद रिक्त चल रहे हैं। परिणाम यह है कि एक या दो शिक्षकों से ही पूरे विद्यालय की शिक्षा व्यवस्था चलवाई जा रही है।

गुणवत्ता की दृष्टि से तो स्थिति और भी खराब है एक ओर हम सभी के लिए शिक्षा का अभियान चला रहे हैं तो दूसरी तरफ लाखों बच्चों को केवल अक्षर ज्ञान करा देने की धोखा धड़ी कर रहे हैं और राष्ट्र की भावी पीढ़ी के भविष्य को अन्धकारमय बना रहे हैं। उच्च शिक्षा की स्थिति भी कुछ इससे अच्छी नहीं है। आखिर कब तक ऐसा चलेगा? आखिर कब तक हम भारत के पढ़े लिखे कहे जाने वाले प्रबुद्ध नागरिक भी अपनी ओर से कोई अपनी पहल न करके सरकार की तरफ निहारते रहेंगे। हम यह उम्मीद करते हैं कि आप अपने नये तार्किक विचारों को हमारे शोध प्रकाशन में प्रकाशित करते हुए शिक्षा की गुणवत्ता को बनाए रखने वाले इस यज्ञ में अपना अमूल्य योगदान देते रहेंगे।

धन्यवाद.....

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INDEX

S. No.	Particulars	Page No.	
		From	To
1	English Papers	E-1	E-21
2	Hindi Papers	H-1	H-42

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8395365 (This DOI is not applicable for separate papers)

INDEX (English)

S. No.	Particulars	Subject	Paper ID	Page No.	
				From	To
1	Participation of Women in Panchayati Raj Institution Manoj Kumar Sahu,Puruna Baripada,Odisha, India	Political Science	17504	E-1	E-9
2	Queer Voices, Stories, and Representation in Modern English Literature Vaishnavi Shah,Bharatpur,Rajasthan, India	English	17652	E-10	E-16
3	Theoretical Approach to the Grasping of Geography Mamta Verma,Dholpur,Rajasthan, India	Geography	18082	E-17	E-21

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8395365 (This DOI is not applicable for separate papers)

INDEX (Hindi)

S. No.	Particulars	Subject	Paper ID	Page No.	
				From	To
1	सिरोही जिले में शस्य संयोजन का एक भौगोलिक अध्ययन अंकित जैन, निवाई, टोंक, राजस्थान, भारत	भूगोल	17122	H-1	H-6
2	सार्वजनिक-भूमि प्रबंधन: मौर्य राज्य और वर्तमान राजस्थान राजेंद्र प्रसाद अग्रवाल, विद्यानगरी, झुंझुनू, राजस्थान, भारत राम दर्शन विद्यानगरी, झुंझुनू, राजस्थान, भारत	लोक प्रशासन	17631	H-7	H-19
3	स्वतंत्रता से पूर्व राजस्थान की राजनीति में महिलाओं की भूमिका निर्मला सैनी, अलवर, राजस्थान, भारत	राजनीति विज्ञान	17651	H-20	H-28
4	कृषि ऋणों में ग्रामीण बैंको का योगदान -आरएमजीबी बैंक के सन्दर्भ में प्रसेन पंवार, पाली, राजस्थान, भारत कुलदीप राखेचा पाली, राजस्थान, भारत	लेखा एवं व्यवसायिक सांख्यिकी	17690	H-29	H-34
5	राजस्थान के सिरोही जिले में भूजल संसाधनों की स्थिति एवं प्रबन्धन सुनील बैरवा, टोंक, राजस्थान, भारत	भूगोल	17536	H-35	H-42

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